
The Role of Social Media in Growth of the Muslim Society (An Analytical Study)

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Abstract

Social Media is unique of the best key people to create original social message by new information technology among, friends, and people and family. Allah SWT who has produced all human being in the world; all thing of the world has been produced for human's welfare, His purpose of beings was that all human being will worship Him, one of the most worships is to help another anyway, for example, It will be beneficial technologically in the present. These learning objectives can be giant through using the Social Media sites in the Muslim community. So, it is used for building of Islamic society and its all Institutions. In the current technology when persons are habituated to factual belongings, consumption and resources it is not calm to get them back to the unseen world. Thus current IT software can be an active for Islamic Teaching. "Social Media" sources like Google+, Tumblr, Instagram Twitter, YouTube, Skype, LinkedIn, IMO, WhatsApp, Facebook, Telegram, etc. are easy to use, smooth, fast communication, live streaming, Face to Face Talk and cheap in numerous forms of our lives from anyplace in the modern ages where traditionally mean that ancient conversation was working slowly but expensive. Now the use of public Media is creative and qualitative in its approach. It has been changed into a form of a data collection device. Similarly, books, journals and online sources were used for research. Reporting on the conversation, "Social Media" has both merits and demerits implications for our Muslim community apparently from a religious perspective. The research reveals that a large number of Muslim society is the user of this Mass Media for the growth and construction of the Muslim Society.

Keywords: Unique, Welfare, Learning, Community, Technology, Software, Communication.

INTRODUCTION

In the Current Times, communication and interaction among the people has totally different by the advent due to creation of Social Media Networks, computers. Societal associations have started the opening of the web and other types of Social Media. People are making relationships, sharing /different thing and vision to give the benefits to the public by using the tools and different sources of Public media, the common man have changed in a well-informed, well freshed knowledge and in the form of well-educated member of Social Society. Especially the Social media playing very important role in the growth and sustainable development of Muslim Society. This public media made very easy to gain the knowledge and education of Islam in the fields of Quran, Hadith, Fiqh, Islamic history, Comparative study of different religion, Islamic, Political, Social, Economic thoughts and Arabic language and literature. The Social Media has made easy to know the way and method of good recitation of the Holy Quran. Now the Muslim researcher are finalized their research about the stability of Muslim society with the using the internet's and different websites. So the man has changed

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himself in this world of Social Media.

In this Study, Social Media is involved in the popular Islamic revolution. Public Media is a big way for a broad viewers and everybody is recognized for Social Media. A few years ago, we used to use text messaging. Those methods were not very advanced and there was little chance of the issue of reform and decreasing the bounds of Islamic impact consequently.

"Today, the adoption of social media and the use of various human life at all levels. Muslims are no different from other organizations, over the past few years, which have increased the use of social media. It has brought about changes that can have a profound effect on the individual and collective levels of the Muslim community. Social media is easy to use, easy to read, and able to communicate at high speed". (1)

Greatest of the difficulties at stake in securing Social Media actions and behavior could change for groups of Islamic society. "But the lack of control and equality today, these tools test the fight against crime, an anti-Muslim morality that preaches Islam to be used for re-transmission". However, we describe someone of the encouraging effects of Islam and its demerit and merit attitudes described by the good practice of exercising its power through the part of "Social Media" in promoting the Islamic Civilization. The study is expected to boost the future of Muslims in spreading Islamic teachings to establish the Muslim Society, improving the usage of Social Media in the Islamic service. According to the good recommendation of the "Quran and Sunnah" for the advantage of humanities, especially the essential to apply it.

Social Media is playing an good role in Modern life, Media is a technology online device that allow people to create and learnt latest news, interact with new people share ideas and societies. It has transformed the method people live their lives today, building conversation much easy.

Different thinkers and scholars have defined Social Media as follows:

"Allows the exchange of user-generated content such as data, photos, and videos. Social media platforms can appear in a variety of ways such as blogs, forums, podcasts, microblogs, photo sharing, Products/service updates, weblogs, etc. Studies have shown that the vast majority of people spend 25% of their time on social media, which further indicates how appropriate and popular social media platforms have become in recent times. The importance of Social Media can be seen in many fields such as business, entertainment, food, lifestyle, well-being and many others. It is important for any business because as an entrepreneur you own the product and with the help of social media companies to communicate with their customers and get important information about them that can increase the value of their product. Most entrepreneurs and retailers have successfully used this platform when it comes to reaching out to potential clients". (2)

"Social media is primarily an online-based tool for sharing and sharing information with people." (3)

"Category of sites based on user participation and user-generated content. It includes social networking sites such as LinkedIn, Facebook, or My Space, social media sites such as Delicious, social media sites such as Digg or Simpy, and other user-focused sites." (4)

"Social media is a video, audio, text or user-produced multimedia activity that is published and shared on a social media site, such as a blog, wiki or video hosting site." (5)

"An umbrella term that describes a variety of functions including technology, social media,

and word building and imagery." (6)

"Software tools allow teams to generate content and participate in peer-to-peer discussions and exchange of content (examples are YouTube, Flickr, Facebook, Myspace etc." (7)

"Social Media is a collection of tools and online spaces available to help individuals and businesses accelerate their knowledge and communication needs." (8)

Social media receive messages in as limited words as imaginable, in as short a period as imaginable, as several people as imaginable (9)

Now I introduce the Islamic Society. It is defined as:

"A society in which Islamic culture dominates". It is also called the Muslim community.

Simply put, defined as a community "people in a defined area are a group of connected cultural cultures" (10)

Islamic society "of a coherent and peaceful society, an organization built according to the divine law" (11)

Some scholars have used the word Ummah instead of the Muslim community. They quoted the verses from the "Holy Quran". In this study, the words "Ummah" and the village "(Kuraiya)" are recognized for the community. (12)

Allah (SWT) stated in the Holy Quran about the Islamic Ummah as:

"تلك أمة قد خلت لهما ما كسبت ولكم ما كسبتم ولا تسألون عما كانوا يعملون(13)"

"That was a community that had already gone before. For them is what they earned and for you is what you have earned. And you will not be accountable for what they have done".

"ذلك أن لم يكن ربك مهلك القرى بظلم وأهلها غفلون(14)"

"This 'sending of the messengers' is because your Lord would never destroy a society for their wrongdoing while its people are unaware 'of the truth'".

In Islamic society, Ummah, a majority of people who are taking fruits and objectives and those who want to go to development and progress have the same goals.

Therefore, the term Islamic Ummah is to describe society. The Ummah is "defined as a universal society in which the highest possible enrollment from nations or societies, but also the social order of Muslims is limited to their particular commitment". It displays that a creature who believes in the Holy Law, bound with Muslims, and is an important factor in Muslim society.

In my view, which is easily described as a Muslim community, and each area for a long time to integrate Islam with the divine laws, and to improve their relations and the continuation of their activities is controlled.

POSITIVE ASPECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON MUSLIM SOCIETY

The Social Media is a basic need for a civil society and its individuals because everybody wants to be aware for latest information and modern knowledge about Islam and other discipline of life. This is due to the Social Media that every members of Islamic society know the different website, Facebook from which he can take the information and education about the Islam and its teaching. In modern times a large number of people are not depending on daily Newspaper, Magazine, Journals, Smartphone and I-Phone but they are using all the sources of Social Media.

Using social media, people completely erase geographical distances from human communication.

“Social media has become very popular in many other communities even without the use of ordinary people. As a non-governmental organization, non-governmental organization and non-governmental organization Social Media has a very effective role in networking with friends and family in interacting with government departments and departments, raising awareness of the Muslim community at grassroots level and developing retailer business. Social media has become a major platform for publishing a wide range of publications with ideas for the entire Muslim community, editing information, promoting information, marketing products, and organizing protests. There are many benefits to social media”. (15)

Source of interaction

Having Social Media you can explore a missing colleague, a virtual or associate. To know there final position. And can consult their thinking on any subject with the closest colleagues and society members. Everybody can communication view of your state to another state, and millions of people all over the world. The thinking and direction of his state and society to another individual in this vast world.

Allah (SWT) said in the Holy Quran:

"يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا قُوا أَنفُسَكُمْ وَأَهْلِيكُمْ نَارًا وَقُودُهَا النَّاسُ وَالْحِجَارَةُ عَلَيْهَا مَلَائِكَةٌ غِلَاظٌ شِدَادٌ"

“O you who have believed, protect yourselves and your families from a Fire whose fuel is people and stones, over which are [appointed] angels, harsh and severe; they do not disobey Allah in what He commands them but do what they are commanded”.(16)

Encouragement of Socialization

Now the world has come in the form of glob owing of using the Social Media. From every corner, an individual can take see and communicate with any other, groups, community successfully.

Now is the age of technology. The whole world has become a valley now for the benefit of technology. Social media can send or share videos or photos; Find Communications; Friends profile is visible; various festivals are available; a conversation can be made; Message can be sent; Games will play. Most importantly, it takes a lot of time to find friends in real life, social media can be built more easily than 'Friends Circle'. You may invite old friends to a social network, make new friends, and invite others outside of their circles”.

All these development in the world, this technological development is much special for Muslims and Muslims alike.

Allah (SWT) said:

"نَمَا الْمُؤْمِنُونَ إِخْوَةٌ فَأَصْلِحُوا بَيْنَ أَخَوِيكُمْ وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ لَعَلَّكُمْ تُرْحَمُونَ"

“The believers are but brothers, so make reconciliation between your brothers and fear Allah that you may receive mercy”(17)

Allah (SWT) said on another place the Holy Quran:

وَالْمُؤْمِنُونَ وَالْمُؤْمِنَاتُ بَعْضُهُمْ أَوْلِيَاءُ بَعْضٍ يَمُرُّونَ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَيَنْهَوْنَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ وَيُقِيمُونَ
لِصَلَاةٍ وَيُؤْتُونَ الزَّكَاةَ وَيَطِيعُونَ اللَّهَ وَرَسُولَهُ أُولَئِكَ سَيَرْحَمُهُمُ اللَّهُ إِنَّ اللَّهَ عَزِيزٌ حَكِيمٌ

“The believers, both men and women, are guardians of one another. They encourage good and forbid evil, establish prayer and pay alms-tax, and obey Allah and His Messenger. It is they who will be shown Allah’s mercy. Surely Allah is Almighty” (18)

Teaching the Quran, Hadith

Hazrat Usman (R.A) Narrated that the Messenger of Allah (SWT) said, خيركم من تعلم القرآن وعلمه
"The greatest between you (Muslims) are persons who learn the Qur'an and teach it." (19). There is no doubt that this great work, the media, there is no uncertainty today that gives us unlimited opportunities to attain this spiritual exaltation before Allah (SWT). Today Muslims have unlimited ways to learn online in Arabic, Tajweed and social media and the Internet in many ways. Now people are comfortable in the comfort of their homes reading the words of the Quran. The Islamic Internet Website is an answer and question section, which is sincerely provided by Deen's Certified Ulama. References, etc. have become much easier. Earlier It was difficult to collect the verses of the Quran.

"In the case of the Quran, Hadiths and Islamic references, the software of 'Maktaba Shamla' is good. This includes books and journals of various topics. It is necessary to know its use in conducting Islamic research in modern times". (20)

So, Thoughts using Mobile Apps, Internets .Instagram and different websites a person can learn and teach the knowledge of the Quran and Hadith. A lot of tafaseer and Ahadeeth books are present on many. Websites for study of the public. In olden times this facility was not available.

Preaching and Da'wah

Preaching and Da'wah is great component of Islamic teachings. Through Da'wah the Ulamas, learned personality and preachers disseminate the lesson of adopting goodness and avoiding from any type of evil.

Allah Ta'ala said in the Holy Quran:

"ولتكن منكم امة يدعون الى الخير ويامرون بالمعروف وينهون عن المنكر واولئك هم المفلحون" (21)

"Let there be a group among you who call 'others' to goodness, encourage what is good, and forbid what is evil it is they who will be successful".

Da'wah will not be barred from working only in Khanka, Mosque, Organization, religious meetings and scriptures. At current, in the age of "Digital Technology", how other religious people address their religious work around the world, similar them, we can preach about our great Islamic education quickly and simply.

The Prophet (peace be upon him) said:

"كلكم راع وكلكم مسئول عن رعيته" (22)

"You are all responsible and every one of you will be asked about subordinate".

It is said in the Holy Qur'an that the principles of Dawah:

"ادع الى سبيل ربك بالحكمة والموعظة الحسنة وجادلهم بالتي هي احسن ان ربك هو اعلم بمن ضل عن سبيله وهو اعلم بالمهتدين"

"Invite (all) to the Way of thy Lord with wisdom and beautiful preaching; and argue with them in ways that are best and most gracious" (23).

It is noteworthy that right here the message of Islam is stored extensive and no longer confined to a specific challenge. This consists of all of the techniques and substances of the invitation. Looking at this verse, it is able to be said that the technology of current generation can be carried out to Muslims for the cause of looking for that era.

The Prophet (SAW) said:

"Convey (my teachings) to the people even if it were a single sentence" (24).

Any further, its miles vital for the media to use it in the context of the Islamic invitation and Tablig. When you speak approximately Islam and its splendor in the media, it spreads in the instances of the arena in every nook of the globe.

“Social Media” strives to unfold the actual message of Islam to the sector. In advance, the leader of Islam had to speak to Muslims approximately many sports and meditation. However now it isn't always essential. it's miles viable to without problems achieve the purpose of staying indoors through the media. Additionally, Many Islamic Scholars, researchers and Teachers lots of different Islamic pupils, use social media as a means of promoting Da'wah.

The Prophet Muhammad (SAW) said:

“Make things easy and do not make things difficult. Give glad tidings and do not repel people”⁽²⁵⁾. Now that human beings are sitting at home or sitting in their dwelling quarters, they're capable of collect facts approximately Islam with internet generation. With the addition of exact public donations, knowledge has entered the hands of generations of those who recognize them. Now not the first-class Muslims, however a Muslim can want precise good fortune without delay to non-Muslims. Call within the know-how of the welfare of all the servants of Allah regardless of party or faith.

SOURCE OF GAINING FRESH RESEARCH

Social media has delivered humans closer to crossing the range. There are some quite simple tales and stories to be discovered on those links. It is not too pricey to be a member of. Similarly, few instructors can easily manage it. Dependence on newspapers, radio and TV on information has been reduced more than ever before. On line magazines can play a widespread position in social alternate and the higher cycle of society. There may be no other way to promote data to the media. What's taking place nationally and the world over, all of which get instant access to fb, Twitter, YouTube, Google and different social networks?

Spreading cognizance, elevating focus, and amassing, disseminating facts, advertising and Media marketing merchandise, and organizing protests around the arena are the fruits of Social Media.

JOB DETAILS INFORMATION

Now a days every qualified person wants the seek the job. All organizations who intend to hire the person use Social Media to give their advertisements on Internet.

“Now almost all government agencies, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and NGOs all have social media pages. There are many projects based on social media pages. “And all of these pages are related to youth-related youth issues. Organizing ideas and organizing visual conferences through social media to discuss and evaluate the various NGOs and their activities”.⁽²⁶⁾

Information on jobs and expertise development on social media pages in various market areas.

“In the modern world, Learning of Islam is one of the media website and publishes free books online, uploading scanned copies or using Islamic images in advertisements. So, many people use social media for learning of Islamic teachings”.⁽²⁷⁾

Social Media also assists the Muslim Society in the following areas:

COMMUNICATION:

Informal communication destinations, for example, Facebook, Twitter, and Google+ have made it simple to interface with individuals and send them messages via looking for their names on the web. Cell phones likewise assumed a vital part, beforehand you expected to have a PC or PC, however presently you can interface with every one of your companions and family members in a hurry, in any event, maintaining a business in a hurry is exceptionally normal.

PHOTO SHARING:

With the approach of Facebook, Instagram, and Snapchat, one would now be able to share photographs about the best snapshots of our lives with loved ones part miles from us. Individuals have been denied of such things previously and presently they are simply too youthful to even think about offering heartfelt minutes to their friends and family sitting miles away.

NEGATIVE ASPECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON THE MUSLIM SOCIETY

Web-based Media is one of the most integral assets for getting the news out essentially at little expense and with little exertion. It has now turned into a worldwide wonder that has changed lives. In certain spaces, the Internet is viewed as unlawful, however in certain spots there are no limitations.⁽²⁹⁾ Also, online networks and gatherings are simply allowed to granulate, where young ladies and young men are effectively hoodwinked. Regardless of how well known they will be, they will have some regrettable characteristics! Furthermore, in case clients don't know about these components, well known media can undoubtedly imperil their daily routines, and they might even destroy their lives. There is another unfairness.

DIVERSITY OF SOCIETY

One media, the variety of society, paying little mind to its consequences for the right to speak freely of discourse, the philosophy of Islam, yet additionally of assorted people groups, not just the perspective on vicious nature, there is no opportunity of articulation.

As indicated by analyst Professor Dr. Mohit Kamal: We used to go out in the field as a youngster. There is no field yet. The youngsters live in the house. Presently their diversion implies online media. At the point when they talk, they talk. Therefore, human correspondence has been seriously harmed. Our youngsters are sluggish. Their real capacity diminishes drastically. Their capacity to acquire or lose power is decreased. Their intellectual ability is reduced. At whatever point they fall into the void, they can't receive in return⁽²⁸⁾.

Furthermore, openness to high-chance sex is a characteristic propensity. This Social Media can be handily found on young ladies, beaus are accessible. Because of such correspondence, human feelings are not restricted to one spot. The change is progressing. This relationship is unfavorable to one's wellbeing. There are awful gatherings all over the place, even here. These gatherings distinguish young ladies, straight housewives. Make a drawn out relationship, then, at that point a corrupt relationship, and the video is indecent.

CREATES PROBLEMS AT WORK

Dependence via online media and its maltreatment cannot just mischief the family and the individual level, yet it can likewise make issues for your work. As of late, we have found in Muslim people group that the inquiry and-answer service happens via online media! All types of public examination are addressed in these methodologies, which have prompted debacle the board, including a wide range of managerial capacities.

In spite of the utilization of web-based media, bogus data about religion has spread, and endeavors have been raised to work up hell for individuals of various religions and homes. Numerous triumphs are fruitful. They used to utilize a great deal of online media, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Google Plus, and so on to make reports.

"Today's media coverage does not cover anything that is good for Islam, but Islam to influence public opinion, often a one-sided system of doctrine or misrepresentation. Muslim conflict in the Western media is often a sign of" Islam ".⁽²⁹⁾

Social media has spread rumors about Muslim leaders and misconceptions about Muslims. A non-Muslim society that views this view considers Muslims as traitors and terrorists.

INCREASING SOCIAL ADDICTION, CRIME AND CORRUPTION

Impulse type is made among correspondence customers. As a general rule is spent, rest upset. In this way, online media is making customers crazy. By virtue of this online media impulse, we molded a social event of dumb youngsters. Without certified life, no thought, no feelings, grandpa takes haven in the grave bed or buddy's grave; Waking up the whole evening resting the whole day using electronic media, Writing, getting falls. Infringement executed against them just as against bad behavior. However, it is said that, along these lines, our young people's respect for women or men has been lost. One gives a succinct response to the following. Food conditions are made between them. Associations among our youth are declining. They lose their individual. Thusly, they are locked in with any kind of bad behavior, yet they don't get it.

SPRADING FALSE STORIES AND RUMORS

According to CNN's Social Report on this popular news channel, unfounded news is being circulated on social media, creating negative media coverage about the media.

"According to experts, social media is used to spread lies and stories. It is found that including Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, Snapchat, etc., Sites in Muslim communities are also useless and full of filth. These sites are being abused. Most blogs are not very organized, writing those blogs are just as fun".⁽³⁰⁾

Allah said about rumors in the Holy Quran:

"يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا إِن جَاءَكُمْ فَاسِقٌ بِنَبَأٍ فَتَبَيَّنُوا أَن تُصِيبُوا قَوْمًا بِجَهْلَةٍ فَتُصْبِحُوا عَلَىٰ مَا فَعَلْتُمْ نَادِمِينَ"

"O you who have believed, if there comes to you a disobedient one with information, investigate, lest you harm a people out of ignorance and become, over what you have done, regretful".⁽³¹⁾

It has been said also:

"ولا تقف ما ليس لك به علم ان السمع والبصر والفؤاد كل اولئك كان عنه مسؤولا"⁽³²⁾

"Do not follow that of which you have no knowledge. Surely the hearing, the sight, the heart - each of these shall be called to account".

INCREASING CRIME AND CORRUPTION

Addiction type is created among communication users. Most of the time is spent, sleep disturbed. For these reasons, social media is driving users crazy. Because of this social media addiction, we formed a group of stupid teenagers. Without physical life, no thought, no feelings, grandpa takes refuge in the grave bed or friend's grave; Waking up all night asleep all day using social media, Writing, reading falls. Not only crimes committed against them but also against crime. But it is said that, as a result, our young people's respect for women or men has been lost. One gives a brief response to the other. Food conditions are created between them. Relationships among our youth are declining. They lose their character. Because of this, they are involved in any kind of crime, but they do not understand it.

Trying to insult a person by spreading falsehood against him, if he is out of his ideology, then now this is a fashion of man. In the Holy Quran, Allah said,

ومن يكسب خطيئة او اثما ثم يرم به برياً فقد احتمل بهتاناً واثماً مبيناً

“And whoever commits an evil or sinful deed then blames it on an innocent person, they will definitely bear the guilt of slander and blatant sin”.⁽³³⁾

The sign of Hypocrite spreading lies or rumors. The Holy Prophet (peace be upon him) said, Conflict organizations use social media to manage their activities and organize themselves. These take the help of social media to manage their terrorist activities and employ them in youth organizations. They have online magazines Report of the Islamic State They create a lot of online content and leave it on social media. In this way, they encourage young people to join. Most young people are taught to talk online and move privately to socialize. But when it is used as a means of disseminating media or military media instead of being used as social media, the sect becomes increasingly anti-social and intolerant than socialism.

“The proof of the Hypocrite is three: When he speaks a lie, When the promise breaks, And when he is kept in the deposit, he is miserable”.⁽³⁴⁾

Due to the overuse of social media, there can be many problems with attention. Inability to remember many things in real life, indifference to words. The hardest students are in this situation. They spend most of their time here and do not worry about studying. Due to the prolonged use of social media, there is a continuous view of the mobile screen, which can lead to headaches and eye problems. With this, the vision diminishes. They cannot adapt to social events because of overuse of people themselves. Due to excessive use of social media, the disease is very common. Because at that time people are determined to limit their contact with the real world. So that the user is connected to the physical world itself, not the real world.

CONCLUSION

The idea of correspondence in the cutting edge universe of present day innovation and online media is utilizing a developing pattern, where the reason for this review was just essential for the Muslim people group. Advantages of informal communication locales influencing effectiveness, genuine Islamic instructing, protection of social connections, and so on Introduced in the information source. Long range informal communication destinations have become very famous. What assumes a key part in carrying distance to the earth? Bo and its kin will benefit on the off chance that they utilize positive perspectives to stay away from negative parts of mindfulness. As a rule, the adverse consequences of media and

correspondence are many, however not just the job of Islam and the job of religion like Islam yet additionally the advantages of sports in the growth of Islamic Society.

There is no innovative item or mechanical turn of events, which has not been applied to Muslims. In any case, recollect, everything can be utilized for acceptable work, and it very well may be utilized for awful purposes. There is nothing bad about materials or innovation. All things considered, the client is capable. In this period of data innovation, there has been a chance for stable belief of Tawhid and Prophethood of the Holy Prophet (PBUH) can be done through Social Media effectively. By making the most of this chance, the lessons of the Quran and Sunnah ought to be brought to the anyway. So, the using of Social Media is also a source of preaching, learning, and Teaching of Islam which stables the Islamic Society.

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